

Best Astrology Books for Beginners

52 Comments / English Blogs, Predictive Astrology / By Deepanshu Giri

Looking for best astrology books for beginners?

I have written some of the real essentials Astrology books for beginners only but these books will not only help you get started in **Jyotish** but also to understand the subject very well- Please go through it. I have added Amazon links below to avoid any confusion. The list contains both Hindi and English as well.

I have over 1200 books in which some of them are manuscripts, some handwritten and I haven't come across a book that hasn't taught me anything as sometimes it's not the time that you will get the essence of the book, As if you are mentally prepared the book will start revealing everything you need to know and beyond it and even a single sentence will start giving you cramps due to happiness and the same book will seem ordinary for some other person.

I have written some of the real essentials one's only but these books will not only help you get started in **Jyotish** but also to understand the subject very well- Please go through it. I have added Amazon links below to avoid any confusion. The list contains both Hindi and English as well.

Its all about how we perceive anything in life or appreciate the beauty of the book- Venus Rahu combo/ 2nd lord with Rahu/Rahu connection to 2nd house will make sure you see and value things beyond normal -which very few people can see- The stronger the connection get- the power to see the value in any person/object increases while Jupiter in 2nd or aspecting second house can hardly judge wrong or right, I have explained that earlier as well.

Astrology Books For Beginners in English

1. My Experience with Astrology

The book is about the Journey of Dr. B.V Raman on how he became Jyotish and the challenges he faced, This book will grip you as not only you will learn several principles of Jyotish but also how Jyotish really calls you.

[Amazon Link](#)

2. How To Judge Horoscope | Part - 1 and 2 -B.V Raman

This is really a good book to see how to quickly analyze any house and rules related to a particular house in any chart.

An old astrologer Bansal Ji use to say- If you can read only this book -you become a half astrologer and he was not wrong as the book contains a lot of information.

[Amazon Link](#)

3. Fundamentals of Astrology - R.K Bhat

This is another good book to understand every house- I recommended it various times to see significations of houses and planets- In this book as well as in Lal-Kitab -5th house is referred as Umbrella while in another classic -I found Moon as Umbrella and body odor to be seen from 7th and same is for the perfume, Why i am telling you to pay attention these minor details as this will be used in remedy and predictions later on- Such as Mars in 7th in Gemini Sign will make a perfume which is made of Tulips or similar fragrance.

[Amazon Link](#)

4. Advance Techniques of Predictive Astrology

This is a good book with lot of reasoning and covering almost every topic in Jyotish and definitely recommended to read even if you have spent some years in Jyotish as well.

[Amazon Link](#)

5. Book of Nakshatra Pad - by Deepanshu Giri Ji

The reason to write the decoded Karam Vipak Samhita was as this was available in several other authors, lot of people published it but no one was writing what I want to read the deeper meaning of a subject, Something which was not available or written by anyone. It is only blessings of Lord Shiv due to whom we are capable to produce this work, I would request all readers to pray to Lord Shiv before reading this book to grant you wisdom and understanding so you can even read what I am not able to write.

Buy Now

6. Compendium of Marriage by Mridula Trivedi

This book although covers marriage in detail but also teaches several principles of Jyotish which can be applied to any chart- This book really helped with all doubts related to marriage issues as there are several examples given in the book.

[Buy Now](#)

Best Astrology books for beginners in Hindi

7. Dev Vichar Mala by H. N Katie

This has been referred by K.N Rao Ji several time when he quotes H.N Katve -It has several gems which no other book contains such as Moon in sign of Mercury will give business related to flowers but also name will be also associated with flower only so very different list of significations are in these books.

[Buy Now](#)

8. Sachitra Jyotish Shiksha

This is another gem of books that comes in the set but contains almost everything a beginner needs – I still refer to it as it contains everything from start to end.

[Buy Now](#)

I believe if you can read at least 2 of the above-listed books- you are good to go as this will give you a better understanding of the subject and get you started.

Want to Learn Astrology Online?

Then do visit link below, i have explained in detailed about all the sources which you ever needed to learn astrology, Find all the sources to learning astrology

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52 thoughts on “Best Astrology Books for Beginners”

GAGAN RISHI

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:10

Thanks ?

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:10

Thank you for sharing wisdom dir?

Reply

SHITAL BAROT

14 JUNE 2020 AT 08:03

We are grateful you have shared this

Reply

NIKHIL

16 JUNE 2020 AT 12:00

Deepanshu ji, thank you for giving out the names of these books. Also, can you point out a book which discusses in detail about the sign qualities. Thank you.

Reply

RAMKISAN GOPALA

28 OCTOBER 2022 AT 16:37

Thanks you!! I will searching in your videos for your recommended book... Finally found here!

Reply

RAMKISAN GOPALA

28 OCTOBER 2022 AT 16:38

*was

BHAVANA

21 FEBRUARY 2023 AT 17:42

Thank you Sir for sharing book names 🙏

Reply

A VERMA

13 AUGUST 2020 AT 17:12

Thank you ?

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:15

Sir can you please clarify that point about jupiter in 2nd not knowing right from wrong or atleast give the link to the video where you have explained it .

Reply

DEBADRI CHATTERJEE

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:20

Sir can you clarify that point about jupiter in 2nd not knowing right from wrong or atleast give me the link to the videi where you have explained it.

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:32

Thanks for sharing about books

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:41

Thanks Guru ji.

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:42

Sir... fundamental astrology par ek hi link...2 baar copy ho gya

Reply

LATIKA KHOLE

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:42

Thank you Sir

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:45

Thank u so much.

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:47

Thanks very much Sir.

Reply

THE ASTRO SECRETS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 16:50

Star Guide to Predictive Astrology by K.B.Parsai is also a good option.

Reply

E S JAGADEESHWAR

13 JUNE 2020 AT 17:01

Thank you, Deepanshu ji. When I was young I regularly read the Astrological magazine of Sri B V Raman during 1980s and 1990s. He was a upasaka of Lord Hayagriva and he used his divine intuition to predict the future of the individual and the country. Naturally the said predictions came into reality.

Secondly <http://www.archive.org> had wonderful old books on Astrology. Varaha Mihira's Brihat Samhita in English more than 1000 pages is also available.

You had more than 1200 books means your knowledge is wonderful. Pure professional with enough experience.

We had 9 planets. If 8 to nil planets are placed in each pada of a nakshatra in each rasi what will happen? If the said rasi or star had benefic or malefic aspects when and what will happen? What are the remedies? specially as per Lal-kitab are known prediction will be proper. May be accurate due to analysis of Divisional Charts, mahardasa and dasaa bhuktis.

For an individual predicting the out come and suggesting suitable remedy are necessary. If the bad is removed, outcome will be good.

Wish God bless you always Deepanshu ji.

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 17:21

Sir can you recommend books which will help us to decode slokas of classical texts

Reply

AMEETD78

13 JUNE 2020 AT 17:59

?????

Reply

SANJEEV SHUKLA

13 JUNE 2020 AT 19:01

This is a wonderful list. Thank you Deepanshu ji!

Reply

SANJEEV SHUKLA

13 JUNE 2020 AT 19:03

Its strange ☰ i was mentally asking Deepanshu ji some of the things that are mentioned in his post

Reply

NAWAL KUMAR.

13 JUNE 2020 AT 20:10

I am 65 years of age, reading astrology for 5 year. Mr Deepanshu is not just well read but has blessings of Divine. God bless him.

Reply

SAPNA

13 JUNE 2020 AT 20:28

Thank u sir

Reply

PRADEEP M

13 JUNE 2020 AT 20:44

Pranam Sir,

I am very happy that you opened this blog to share us your knowledge.

Thank You very much for the list.

After I was advised to study astrology in my Dream, I too started with Raman Sir's Books. But I could not Digest them properly even after reading it a couple of times. I have not found any other books with such standard.

I will start with other books.

Waiting eagerly for your book on Nakshatra!!!

My body gets up headed too much and I started to get health issues so stopped studying astrology.

It would be of great help if you to share some information on the problems that Astrologers face and remedies & rituals that has to be followed.

Reply

BALRAM SHARMA

13 JUNE 2020 AT 21:01

Thankyou for your kind advise , some time a gud advice opens gateway to wisdom for someone ,hope it will help all the dvine knowledge seekers.

Reply

BV

13 JUNE 2020 AT 21:39

Whoa☰you are amazing!! This is just what I waiting for☰unless these books are out of stock everywhere:(

Venus-Rahu is after all not so bad I guess☰..as cited everywhere. It does help us appreciate the beauty in everything and everyone around us.

Also, a small request. Hope all your FB posts and You tube videos carry some 3-5 hashtags and the first 3 being the most vital and that☰s what Google picks up for indexing on their platform. That way it can reach a broader audience and the page always comes up in searches☰. for example #jyotish #vedicastrology #eclipse etc as its trending..also under the ☰About us☰ page on FB. Facebook hashtags are a nice touch from a search perspective, allowing you to get more eyes on your posts.

Just something I noticed please. It may take a few days for the algorithms to pick up but it will help eventually.

And yes, as you said in the end we hope ☰that is not it☰ and you keep giving us more! A lot of us look forward to these posts!!

Reply

BNS JANARDHAN RAO

13 JUNE 2020 AT 23:00

Dear Deepanshu ji,

I have developed interest in learning Astrology by watching your YouTube videos.

The knowledge u posses is very rare. I do have an Astrologer with me, who can predict things without looking in horoscope. He is a venus type astro always sees remedies in tantra and mantra running after money.

I was looking to change my job since many of youtube astro channel predicted this year 2020, meen rashi people is having a better job prospects.

I have some problems in financial aspects and also in my martial life.

When i started searching for the planets placements in my lagna chart like ketu in 6th house.

I have come across your videos and developed interest to master this astrology.

I have bought lalkitab, 2 weeks back online and on the same day while seeing a grey colour cat while walking i fell down. Till now i dont want to open the book since i dont see my nimits are encouraging and also i have saturn in 8th house.

I dont know when i will get better job but i would like to learn from you and thank you for sharing knowledge.

God bless you

Regards,

Janardhan

Reply

SONAL SHUKLA

13 JUNE 2020 AT 23:33

Thank you so much sir

Your efforts are so precious but it is a request don't feel bad who are copying you. Master piece is only one and you are the creator of these techniques. Your students will always support n pay back your efforts one day.

Keep going with lot of smile.

Reply

SONAL SHUKLA

13 JUNE 2020 AT 23:34

Thank you so much sir

Your efforts are so precious but it is a request don't feel bad who are copying you. Master piece is only one and you are the creator of these techniques. Your students will always support n pay back your efforts one day.

Keep going with lot of smile.

Reply

ANONYMOUS

13 JUNE 2020 AT 23:42

Google couldn't find any book titled Fundamentals of Astrology- R.K Bhat. But found another book titled Fundamentals of Astrology by M R Bhat. The link given for Book 3 shows Book no 2 instead. Could you please clarify recommendation no 3?

Reply

SHOBHA MARWAH

13 JUNE 2020 AT 23:48

Thank you very much Sir for the list of Books.

Reply

SANJEEV KUMAR PATTNAYAK

14 JUNE 2020 AT 00:37

Thank you sir . For now i will try to learn from these books when I will be able to afford your course I will definitely try to join.

Reply

KERI

14 JUNE 2020 AT 03:20

Hi there,

There might be a small market in converting these books to digital copies. Personally I prefer physical books because seeing them there prompts me to go back to visit different concepts.

Anyway I can't get a copy of these easily without a massive markup + shipping. The first book

sells for 22 x the price (a bit much for me right now) and the others will be significantly higher if I can get them sent to my country at all. Maybe later when the flights come back!

Reply

ANONYMOUS

14 JUNE 2020 AT 10:35

Pl suggest some good book on nakshatra

Reply

ANONYMOUS

14 JUNE 2020 AT 10:52

Sir, the link for Fundamentals of astrology by Mr. Bhat...the link seems wrong. Can you please correct. On check Amazon there seems to be 3 different books.

Reply

BV

14 JUNE 2020 AT 20:27

Here is the book I ordered...RamaKrishna Bhat...RK Bhat.

https://www.amazon.com/gp/aw/d/8120802756?ref=ppx_pt2_mob_b_prod_image

Reply

VIVEK SHARMA

14 JUNE 2020 AT 12:04

Great Works....Sir.When will I get a reply from you Sir....as I've mailed you a couple of times regarding the obvious...thanks n regards....vivek

Reply

SHOUVIK87

15 JUNE 2020 AT 08:05

Thank you sir! this is most helpful

[Reply](#)**BHARATT ARORA**

16 JUNE 2020 AT 23:25

A BIG THANKS SIR
FOR SHOWING THE RIGHT PATH ????

[Reply](#)**JAYME786**

20 JUNE 2020 AT 10:31

Sir @Lunar astro ,there are lots of misconceptions amongst learners regarding VENU RAHU combination and aspect.Please,Can you write an article about this conjunction in d9 chart,as its a fruit of rashi chart.Also,when we talk about venus,immediately spouse comes to mind.So can you write an article on rahu aspect on 7th lord,7th house both in d1 and d9.There is lot of illusion in this combination,as Rahu maharaj is present there ?

[Reply](#)**ABHISHEK JAIN JAIN**

28 JULY 2020 AT 07:36

Apki Sabse acchi baat mujhe yahi lagti aaap book suggest krte hai.

Inme se mostly padhi hai Maine

Meri life Ka ek funda rha jb bhi Mai Kisi scholar se Mila .. unse ashirwad me Kuch books Ka suggestions liya or padha☰ transformation hota gya☰

MANIKYARAO

10 AUGUST 2022 AT 10:18

Thank you so much sir

Reply

INDOPOL4D

28 DECEMBER 2022 AT 03:58

thing will be get worst but this is the good post

Reply

JADWAL TIMNAS

1 JANUARY 2023 AT 05:04

it's been a while when i can found blog with so good information thanks you

Reply

ACE TOTO888

3 JANUARY 2023 AT 08:37

i'm so gratefull that i have found blog so good like this thanks you so much

Reply

ACETOTO888

3 JANUARY 2023 AT 08:37

god i'm so gratefull that i have found blog so good like this thanks you so much

Reply

TOGELSLOT

6 FEBRUARY 2023 AT 02:51

all is good

Reply

ANIL MATHUR

23 MARCH 2023 AT 16:30

Respected sir ji

once again thank you very much for lighting a lamp for the students .

Reply

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